

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

On the drift-diffusion analysis of the Pulsed Townsend experiment: a fitting algorithm and benchmark study

To cite this article: Hanut Vemulapalli *et al* 2026 *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **35** 015014

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Determination of the accuracy of actinometry and line ratio techniques in an O₂ glow discharge: II. Electric field measurements with Ar and Xe admixtures](#)
L Kuijpers, E Baratte, O Guaitella *et al.*
- [Numerical study of surface charge dynamics and its feedback on the interaction between atmospheric pressure plasma jet and dielectric target](#)
Chenhua Ren, Bangdou Huang, Cheng Zhang *et al.*
- [Review of nonequilibrium plasma kinetics in hypersonic flows](#)
Timothy T Aiken, Nicholas A Carter and Iain D Boyd

HIDEN
ANALYTICAL
Trusted in Research
for over 40 years

www.HidenAnalytical.com

Plasma Diagnostics for Fundamental and Applied Research

Mass & energy analysis of ions, neutrals and radicals

ESPion Advanced Langmuir Probe

- Langmuir probes for plasma diagnostics
- RF compensation
- Multiple configuration options available

Find Solutions for Your Research

PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED
13 June 2025REVISED
22 October 2025ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION
10 December 2025PUBLISHED
21 January 2026

Original content from
this work may be used
under the terms of the
[Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 licence](#).

Any further distribution
of this work must
maintain attribution to
the author(s) and the title
of the work, journal
citation and DOI.

On the drift-diffusion analysis of the Pulsed Townsend experiment: a fitting algorithm and benchmark study

Hanut Vemulapalli^{1,3,*} , Mücahid Akbas^{1,3} , Dale Muccignat^{2,3} , Greg Boyle^{2,3} , Ron D White² and Christian M Franck¹

¹ Institute for Power Systems and High Voltage Technology, ETH Zürich, Zürich 8006, Switzerland

² College of Science & Engineering, James Cook University, Townsville QLD4814, Australia

³ These authors contributed equally to this work.

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: hvemulapa@ethz.ch

Keywords: swarm parameters, low-temperature plasmas, skewness, Pulsed Townsend

Abstract

Electron transport properties in gases and gas mixtures can be determined from measurements with a Pulsed-Townsend experiment. Analytical solutions of a drift-diffusion equation are fitted to the measured experimental waveforms to determine electron transport coefficients. However, it is not always unambiguously clear what the published measurement data ultimately represents, under which assumptions published transport data have been derived, and how large the uncertainty is. To address this, we first present an open source code for the analysis of the Pulsed-Townsend experiment waveforms. We then use this code to fit synthetic waveforms generated by Monte-Carlo simulations to estimate the accuracy of transport data obtained by curve fitting. Two benchmark simulation cases are considered: a representative case that closely replicates a typical Pulsed-Townsend experiment and an idealised case that replicates the assumptions that underpin the state of the art analytic solution. For each case simulations are performed for three different gases (Ar, CO₂, and SF₆) and over a wide range of electric field strengths (10–1000 Td), densities (10²²–10²⁴ m⁻³) and electrode spacings (10–30 mm). For the representative model, while the error in the extracted transport coefficients can be as good as 0.1 %, it deteriorates with decreasing pressure, decreasing electrode gap distance and increasing electric field strength. While significantly reduced errors were found for the idealised model, errors exceeding 10 % were still present in some regimes. We show that these errors are strongly correlated with the third-order transport coefficient, which calls into question the accuracy of analyses that do not account for it, especially for experiments operated at low pressures and small electrode spacings.

1. Introduction

Low-temperature plasmas (LTPs) are found in a wide variety of scientific and industrial applications: in the field of medicine [1], semiconductor processing [2, 3], gas insulation [4], gaseous particle detectors [5], spacecraft propulsion and agriculture [6, 7], among others. These plasmas consist of high-energy electrons and heavier species at a lower (or even room) temperature [8]. The transport properties of electrons in the presence of these heavier species, often referred to as swarm data, are of fundamental importance when studying LTPs. This swarm data is commonly used in hydrodynamic models to simulate LTP's [8, 9] or is 'inverted' to obtain electron-scattering cross-section sets [9, 10]. These cross-section sets quantify the probability of different interaction processes between electrons and neutral gas molecules and enable the direct simulation of LTPs.

The Pulsed Townsend (PT) experiment is one method that is used to measure the transport properties of electrons in gases and gas mixtures [11]. A pulse of electrons is released from a photocathode and drifts towards the anode under an applied uniform electric field. The experiment measures the time dependent current induced in the anode due to the drift of electrons and ions.

To obtain swarm data, analytical solutions to a drift-diffusion equation are fitted to the measured induced current waveforms. Several different analytical and numerical solutions to the drift-diffusion equation have previously been used to obtain swarm data from experiments [12], with the state of the art solution being a semi-infinite domain approximation that neglects the presence of an absorbing cathode boundary with a delta function source to describe the initial electron pulse. Using different analytical solutions while fitting leads to different sets of swarm data.

Further challenges arise when the swarm data is ‘inverted’ to obtain electron scattering cross-section sets. The inversion process involves an iterative comparison of the swarm data computed from the best-guess cross-section sets to experimental data until a good match is obtained [13, 14], as depicted in figure 1. As swarm inversion is a problem that admits multiple solutions, several cross section sets can be obtained that match a single set of swarm data. Typically, there is a tendency to over-fit to the mean values of experimentally derived swarm data.

Recent automated data-driven procedures [15–18] improve upon this by implementing artificial noise to also account for, and approximate, experimental error bars. As such, it is vital to clarify what the published experimental swarm data represent, under which assumptions it has been derived, and how large the uncertainty is.

To this end, in section 2 we first present a brief review of the analytical solution to the drift-diffusion equation used when fitting waveforms from the PT experiment. Section 3 outlines the fitting routines employed. In section 4, we describe a Monte-Carlo (MC) simulation framework used to perform two sets of MC simulations: one with experimentally-relevant source distributions and boundary conditions (representative simulated PT, section 5.1), and another that more closely matches the assumptions under which the analytic semi-infinite domain solution is derived (idealised simulated PT, section 5.2). Section 5 presents the transport coefficients extracted from fitting these simulated waveforms using the semi-infinite domain solution. For each case, we consider three gases with a range of reduced electric fields, background densities and electrode spacings. The resulting errors in the extracted swarm parameters are analysed to assess the influence of the source distributions and boundary effects.

The waveform-fitting code is made available online under open access, with the intention of facilitating transparency in determining swarm data from PT measurements and promoting greater consistency in reporting such data across different experimental groups.

Finally, in section 5.3, we examine the role of the third-order transport coefficient in equation (2) and its influence on fitting accuracy.

2. Theory of the PT experiment

The starting point for the description of the electron density evolution is the continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial z} = S(z, t), \quad (1)$$

where z is the external field direction, $n(z, t)$ is the charged-particle density, $\Gamma(z, t)$ is the charged-particle flux, and $S(z, t)$ is the integral over all non-conservative processes such as attachment and ionisation. For a discussion on the derivation of equation (1) from Boltzmann’s kinetic equation, see [12].

In the absence of strong gradients, the space-time dependence of all transport properties can be projected onto the electron density exclusively, such that the flux and source terms can be written as a density gradient expansion [19], and equation (1) becomes:

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + W_b \cdot \frac{\partial n}{\partial z} - D_b \cdot \frac{\partial^2 n}{\partial z^2} + Q_b \cdot \frac{\partial^3 n}{\partial z^3} + \dots = n \cdot R_{\text{net}}, \quad (2)$$

where R_{net} is the effective ionisation rate accounting for ionisation, attachment and other non-conservative processes. The transport coefficients, W_b , D_b and Q_b are understood to be the bulk drift, longitudinal diffusion coefficient, and longitudinal skewness coefficient, respectively. Bulk transport coefficients are defined through the diffusion equation, whereas flux coefficients are defined through flux-gradient relationships (e.g. Fick's law). The two sets of coefficients can differ significantly when non-conservative processes are operative, which was the cause of much historical debate [12, 20–22].

The usual procedure for analysing swarm experiments, such as the PT experiment, is to neglect the third-order (and higher) spatial derivative terms in equation (2) [10]. However, recent publications have highlighted the influence of skewness [23–25], and brought into question the validity of neglecting it (and higher order terms) in the analysis of swarm experiments by demonstrating significant differences in the extracted swarm parameters, especially diffusion [26].

Neglecting third-order and higher-order terms, equation (2) can be solved analytically for various open and bounded system configurations. For an initial Dirac pulse of electron density N_e released at $t = 0$ ($n(z, 0) = N_e \delta(z)$) into an unbounded domain, the solution of the second-order drift-diffusion equation (2) yields:

$$\frac{n(z, t)}{N_e} = \frac{\exp[R_{\text{net}}t]}{\sqrt{4\pi D_b t}} \exp\left[-\frac{(z - W_b t)^2}{4D_b t}\right]. \quad (3)$$

If we then consider an ideal absorbing boundary located at $z = L$, the analytic solution of the drift-diffusion-reaction equation becomes [10, 12, 27]:

$$\frac{n(z, t)}{N_e} = \frac{\exp\left[R_{\text{net}}t + \frac{W_b}{2D_b}(z - \frac{1}{2}W_b t)\right]}{\sqrt{4\pi D_b t}} \left\{ \exp\left[-\frac{z^2}{4D_b t}\right] - \exp\left[-\frac{(z - 2L)^2}{4D_b t}\right] \right\}. \quad (4)$$

A similar infinite series solution can be found for the case of two absorbing boundaries [12, 27].

The PT experiment measures the total electron current between the cathode and anode. For the electron density distribution given in equation (4), this current can be found from:

$$I_e(t) = \frac{qW_f}{L} \int_{-\infty}^L n(z, t) dz, \quad (5)$$

such that,

$$I_e(t) = \frac{I_0}{2} \exp[R_{\text{net}}t] \cdot \left\{ \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{W_b \cdot t - L}{\sqrt{4D_b t}}\right) - \exp\left(\frac{W_b \cdot L}{D_b}\right) \cdot \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{W_b \cdot t + L}{\sqrt{4D_b t}}\right) \right\}, \quad (6)$$

where the quantity W_f is the flux drift velocity, which should not be confused with the bulk drift velocity W_b , $I_0 = \frac{N_e q W_f}{L}$ is the initial current, and erfc represents the complementary error function.

Equation (6) forms the basis of the fitting routine for determining the transport coefficients W_b , D_b and R_{net} from PT waveforms, as discussed in section 3.

3. Fitting routine—APTX

We have developed the curve fitting code APTX (analysis for the Pulsed Townsend experiment), and it is made publicly available over GitLab⁴ for increased transparency and to enable future collaborative improvements. Equation (6) is used to fit the experimental current waveforms. However, to achieve satisfactory curve fitting results, it is necessary to ensure numerical stability with the chosen objective function. In the case of equation (6), the combination of exponential and error function terms leads to numerical issues whenever the ratio W_b/D_b is large. One approach to achieve numerical stability consists of reformulating the second complementary error function expression erfc in equation (6) by using the

⁴ https://gitlab.com/ethz_hvl/APTX, version 1.0.

scaled complementary error function $\text{erfc}(x) = \exp(-x^2) \cdot \text{erfcx}(x)$. The corresponding objective function for optimisation is chosen to be:

$$J_{\text{cost}}(\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{I}_e) = \left\| \frac{\mathbf{I}_e}{I_{e,\text{max}}} - C \cdot \exp(R_{\text{net}}(\mathbf{t} - t_0)) \left[\text{erfc}(\mathbf{x}_-) + \exp\left(2\frac{T_e}{\tau_D} - \mathbf{x}_+^2\right) \cdot \text{erfcx}(\mathbf{x}_+) \right] \right\|_1, \quad (7)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{\pm} &= \frac{(\mathbf{t} - t_0) \pm T_e}{\sqrt{2 \cdot \tau_D \cdot (\mathbf{t} - t_0)}}, \\ T_e &= \frac{L}{W_b}, \\ \tau_D &= 2 \frac{D_b}{W_b^2}. \end{aligned}$$

The constant C denotes a scaling factor, R_{net} the effective ionisation rate, T_e the electron arrival time at the anode, τ_D a characteristic time scale for the longitudinal electron diffusion, \mathbf{t} is the array of sampling times, t_0 the signal delay in the experimental waveform [12, 28, 29], \mathbf{I}_e the array of measured current signal samples, $I_{e,\text{max}}$ the measured current trace peak value and $\|\cdot\|_1$ denotes the L^1 norm. The cost function J_{cost} is then minimised by employing a global optimisation method, here, the genetic optimisation algorithm *differential_evolution* is used, which is available in the *SciPy* library [30]. The use of a global optimisation method enables consistent and accurate curve fitting results in general, which are independent of the investigated gas and operating conditions such as pressure or electric field strength. Advantageously, an initial starting point guess for the optimisation is not required and the use of a properly chosen fixed set of upper and lower optimisation boundaries is sufficient.

Figure 2 illustrates a few representative measured current waveforms and the corresponding curve fits using the implemented equation (6).

The rising edge is cropped within the evaluation in equation (7), as this is a result of the finite pulse width of the pulsed laser, electron emission processes in the photocathode, and measurement bandwidth limitations. These conditions are not reflected in the derivation and the underlying assumptions of equation (6), and will be resolved in future work.

The measurement uncertainties of the experimental setup are described in detail in [11]. The rising edge of the capacitive current waveforms in figure 2 is a convolution of the timescales of the initial electron swarm being released from the photocathode and the minimum rise time that can be resolved due

to the bandwidth of the experimental setup. The falling edge results from electrons being absorbed by the anode and is on the longitudinal diffusion timescale. The intermediate region is characterised by an exponential behaviour, where a flat curve corresponds to zero net electron generation, an increasing slope to net electron ionisation and a decreasing slope to net attachment. Measurement noise (as evident from the shown waveforms) distorts the underlying signal and decreases the curve fitting performance. This noise is most notably due to the statistical nature of electrons, the voltage source, and the measurement signal amplifier.

4. Monte Carlo simulations of the PT experiment

MC simulation techniques are a powerful tool for the simulation of macroscopic properties under realistic experimental conditions [31]. This simulation technique is particularly useful as it is not reliant on the density gradient approximation and not restricted to simple source distributions and boundary conditions. In this work we use the benchmarked MC simulation package developed at James Cook University [32] to investigate the accuracy of fitting routines applied to PT experiments. Figure 3 shows example simulated electron current waveforms in CO₂ gas under different conditions, and the corresponding curve fits using the code from section 3.

A brief overview of the simulation method is provided below.

4.1. Overview

Each electron's path is advanced in discrete time steps between events using standard kinematics given an applied uniform electric field (E) and uniform background molecule density (N). Here, we assume that the density of electrons is sufficiently small and thus has a negligible influence on both the applied electric field and surrounding electrons. At each step, the flight time until all potential events are either sampled from probabilistic distributions or calculated and the event with the shortest flight time is chosen. After the electron's position in phase space is updated given the chosen flight time, the associated event occurs. This process then repeats until some end condition is met.

Events are classified as either collision or sampling events. For collision events, the flight time until the next collision is sampled using the Null Collision technique proposed by Skullerud *et al* [33]. Once a collision event occurs, the collision type is then sampled using the relative magnitudes of each collision frequency evaluated at the relative energy of the binary collision. For each ionising collision for a given electron, the new electron is added to a queue and in the case of an attachment collision, the electron is simply removed from the simulation. Once an end condition is met for a particular electron, the next electron in the queue is simulated. This is repeated until the queue is empty. Here, isotropic scattering is assumed for all collisions and uniform random energy sharing is used for ionisation collisions.

Sampling events allow both for measurements to be recording at consistent points and for boundary conditions to be enforced. The flight time for the electron to reach a region or point of interest in phase space is calculated and the electron is advanced to that point. Any necessary measurements of the electron are then recorded and relevant boundary conditions are enforced.

4.2. Source distributions and boundary conditions

To replicate the PT experiment and equation (6), we implement source distributions and boundary conditions informed by the experimental apparatus at ETH Zurich. The electron density $n(z, t)$ described by equation (4) is represented by a two dimensional array of temporal and spatial sampling points. Each electron is initialised at $z = 0$, where z is directed parallel to the applied electric field. The anode is positioned at $z = L$ while the cathode is positioned at $z = -z_0$ and varied. The distance between the initial electron source and the absorbing cathode serves as an approximation of the complex physics of photocathode emission. The domain for t is chosen as $t = [0, 4T_e]$ and is discretised with intervals of $\Delta t = 10^{-10}$ s to match the resolution achieved in the experiment [11]. At each temporal sampling point, the number of electrons within any given Δz between array elements is recorded.

As equation (6) assumes each electron is initialised under steady-state conditions, a swarm of electrons is first simulated until steady-state is reached. Then, their final velocities are sampled from to determine the initial velocity for each electron in the replication of equation (6).

4.3. Convergence tests

To ensure sufficient statistics are maintained and steady-state conditions are reached in each simulation conducted here, we implement several convergence criteria. To determine the steady-state relaxation time for each simulation, 10^5 electrons are simulated from rest for a short density reduced time of $N \cdot t_i = 10^{13} \text{ s} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$. The mean electron energy is then calculated for the ranges $[\frac{1}{3}N \cdot t_i, \frac{2}{3}N \cdot t_i]$ and $[\frac{2}{3}N \cdot t_i, N \cdot t_i]$.

If the difference between the mean energies is greater than 1%, $N \cdot t_i$ is increased by 25% and the process is repeated.

To account for electron loss or gain, if the number of electrons falls below 7.5×10^4 after $N \cdot t_i$, the initial number of electrons is adjusted such that, on average, 10^5 electrons remain during the last third of the simulation time. In addition, if the number of electrons at the end of the simulation is greater than 10^6 , the initial number of electrons are similarly reduced.

To determine whether each simulated PT current trace has converged, electrons are progressively added to the simulation until the current trace does not meaningfully change. First, 128 electrons are simulated and the resulting current trace is stored. The number of electrons are then doubled until the mean percentage difference between each subsequent current trace profile is less than 0.2%. The 0.2% threshold was chosen as it was sufficient to produce consistent fitted values of the transport coefficients, at reasonable computational cost. Note that for this comparison, the current trace is truncated after it has reached 10% of the initial current value to reduce the impact of negligible current values on the percentage difference calculation.

As an additional verification step, the swarm parameters from the MC simulations are compared with those computed using a multi-term Boltzmann solver developed in previous works (see [34–37] for details).

5. Results

In this section, the accuracy of the curve fitting approach from sections 2 and 3 is investigated, utilising the simulated MC waveforms from section 4. We choose three gases with well established cross-section sets and distinct electron attaching behaviours: Ar (non-attaching), CO_2 (attaching) and SF_6 (highly-attaching). Each cross-section set was taken from the Biagi v7.1 database [38] available on LXCat [39]. We compare the swarm parameters obtained from curve fitting to those computed directly from the MC simulation. We consider two demonstrative scenarios:

- 1) A replication of typical experimental conditions, including a time-dependent electron source and re-absorbing cathode. This will be referred to as the *representative* case.
- 2) Idealised conditions that are consistent with the derivation of equation (6), i.e. a delta function source and a cathode placed at $z = -\infty$. This will be referred to as the *idealised* case.

Table 1. Source distributions and boundary conditions used for the *representative* and *idealised* cases. Each source is represented by a distribution that is sampled by the MC simulation. The parameter σ represents the standard deviation, while $f_{ss}(v)$ is the distribution of electron velocities under steady-state conditions.

	Source	Boundaries
Representative	$\frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{v^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \delta(v)\delta(z)$,	$-z_0 < z < L$
Idealised	$f_{ss}(v)\delta(t)\delta(z)$,	$-\infty < z < L$

Figure 4. Swarm parameters in CO_2 gas from curve fitting with equation (6) to MC simulation waveforms within a setup that approximates the source distributions and boundary conditions of a realistic PT setup. Experimental data at $p \approx 41$ Pa, $p \approx 409$ Pa and $p \approx 4089$ Pa is included for comparison. There are significant deviations present between the swarm parameters obtained from curve fitting and the swarm parameters computed from the CO_2 cross-section set using MC. The swarm parameters from curve fitting also show an apparent pressure dependency, as is the case with the experimental data. Very high relative error percentages in the case of R_{net} are due to the true value of R_{net} being close to 0.

The source distributions and boundary conditions used for each case are shown in table 1. In the following discussions, we provide relative error percentages and absolute errors as,

$$\text{Relative error} = \left| \frac{s_{\text{fit}} - s_{\text{MC}}}{s_{\text{MC}}} \right| \cdot 100\%, \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Absolute error} = |s_{\text{fit}} - s_{\text{MC}}|, \quad (9)$$

where s denotes the value of a given swarm parameter and the subscripts ‘fit’ and ‘MC’ refer to the fitted values and MC calculations, respectively.

5.1. Representative Simulation

Initially, the PT experiment is replicated in the MC simulation setup by placing a cathode at a distance of $z_0 = 10 \mu\text{m}$ from the initial electron swarm at $z = 0$, choosing an initial electron temporal pulse width (full width at half maximum) of $2\sqrt{2\ln 2} \cdot \sigma = 10$ ns, and initialising the electrons with a velocity of $v = 0$. Figure 4 shows the swarm parameters and fitting errors for CO_2 . Equivalent plots for Ar and SF_6 are given in figures 10 and 12 in appendix B.

Some important trends in the fitted swarm parameters can be observed:

- 1) R_{net} at lower pressures has an apparent region of increased error in the attachment coefficient. At low pressures there is significant back-diffusion to the cathode, which is not accounted for by equation (6). This can lead to large uncertainties when fitting the waveforms, as illustrated in figures 9 and 10, and discussed in appendix A.
- 2) The reduced longitudinal diffusion coefficient $N \cdot D_b$ from the curve fitting shows an apparent pressure dependency (as also observed in the experimental measurement data). This may be due to the lack of an absorbing cathode boundary condition or initial source distribution in the derivation of equation (6).
- 3) The deviations in R_{net} and W increase with lower gap distances and pressures. Above approximately 100 Td for Ar, and above the critical field for CO₂ and SF₆, the deviations increase with increasing field strength. In particular, the values from the curve fitting underestimate the true values in this regime.

Here, it is difficult to separate the errors involved with the fitting procedure itself from those that arise due to the approximations and physical effects included/excluded from equation (6). We now consider an idealised situation with source distributions and boundary conditions chosen to be consistent with the derivation of equation (6), to better isolate the errors involved with the fitting procedure.

5.2. Idealised Simulation

In this section, an idealised version of the PT experiment is considered. The cathode is placed far from the initial electron swarm ($z_0 = \infty$) and initialised spatially as a Dirac pulse with velocities sampled from a steady-state electron energy distribution (see section 4.2 for details). These conditions match the underlying assumed source distributions and boundary conditions in the derivation of equation (6). Figure 5 shows the electron swarm parameters for CO₂ obtained by curve fitting with equation (6) to the idealised MC simulation waveforms. Equivalent plots for Ar and SF₆ are given in figures 11 and 13 in appendix B. Notable similarities and differences can be observed vis-à-vis the representative case (section 5.1).

- 1) The R_{net} values more closely match the MC values (ground truth), however a region of apparent (i.e. misattributed) strong attachment is still present at the lowest considered pressure of 10^{22} m^{-3} . In the idealised setup, this cannot be attributed to back-diffusion, as in the representative case.
- 2) While the pressure dependence of the reduced longitudinal diffusion coefficient $N \cdot D_b$ is significantly decreased when compared to the representative case, some pressure dependence still exists. In the idealised setup, this cannot be attributed to back-diffusion or an initial source distribution, as in the representative case.
- 3) Above approximately 100 Td for Ar, and above the critical field for CO_2 and SF_6 , the deviations increase with increasing field strength for all three swarm parameters. The values from curve fitting underestimate the true values in this regime.

Even when the simulations match the conditions under which equation (6) is derived exactly, we still see significant deviations between the fit values and the true values computed with the MC solver. The distinct structures observed in the errors suggest that a physical effect (or multiple effects) is not being sufficiently described by equation (6).

The second-order density gradient expansion approximation is utilised in the solution of equation (2). In what follows, we compare approximate solutions of the third-order density gradient expansion with MC data to quantify the effect of the skewness parameter on the current trace.

5.3. Third order transport parameter: skewness

Even in the idealised simulations there is still a discrepancy between the MC swarm parameters and the ones obtained by curve fitting equation (6) to the MC waveforms. This discrepancy is generally more pronounced at lower pressures and smaller electrode spacings. At the same time, there exists a dependence on E/N that varies across the three gases shown. We investigate the source of these errors by examining the validity of the second-order approximation through the inclusion of the third-order ‘skewness’ transport coefficient, Q_b .

The analytic solutions to the electron density distribution and current waveforms given by equations (4)–(6) are only possible when considering the terms up to second-order in equation (2), i.e. the drift-diffusion equation. To solve the drift-diffusion-skewness equation requires either approximations or numerical solutions. Beginning in 1974, Skullerud [40] and McIntosh [41] analysed the spatial density profile of electrons using a MC simulation and found the electron distribution to be asymmetric in space, which is not captured in the second-order drift-diffusion description. More recently, Penetrante and Bardsley [42] reported an approximate solution of the continuity equation including the third-order coefficient. Simonović *et al* [23–25] have since performed extensive investigations of third-order transport of electron swarms in electric and magnetic fields, elucidating the various skewness component definitions and behaviours, as well as the differences in flux and bulk skewness coefficients.

In one dimension, the free-space solution can be approximated by [23, 42]:

$$n^{(1)}(z, t) \approx n(z, t) \left[1 + Q_b \frac{t(z - W_b t)^3 - 6D_b t^2 (z - W_b t)}{8(D_b t)^3} \right], \quad (10)$$

where Q_b is the longitudinal skewness coefficient and $n(z, t)$ is the usual second-order solution given in equation (3). The two-dimensional solution was given in [23], which then also includes transverse diffusion and skewness coefficients.

MC simulation was used to calculate the value of Q_b under steady-state conditions utilising the expressions given in [25]:

$$Q_b = \frac{1}{6} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\langle z^3 \rangle - 3 \langle z \rangle \langle z^2 \rangle + 2 \langle z \rangle^3 \right), \quad (11)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes an average over time. In general, Q_b can take up to twice as long to converge to steady-state conditions as W_b and D_b . Here, we use numerical differentiation to calculate Q_b , which, as noted by Simonović *et al*, can result in large statistical fluctuations. To ensure that sufficient accuracy is achieved, first, the steady-state time is found. Then after steady-state conditions are met, the standard deviation of Q_b is recorded. If this standard deviation is greater than 5%, the number of initial electrons is doubled and the values are recalculated.

In figure 6, we compare the free-space approximate solution (equation (10)) with an equivalent density profile from the MC simulation at two representative times; 20 and 100 ns.

The CO_2 cross-section set is used with a reduced electric field of 100 Td and a background density of 10^{23} m^{-3} . Note that these conditions and sampling times have been chosen so that the third-order effect

Figure 6. Comparison of electron density using the second-order approximation (dots) and a series approximation to the third-order approximation (dashes) at 20 and 100 ns. Also shown is the equivalent MC simulation (solid), which is in good agreement with the third-order solution. CO₂ is simulated at 100 Td with a background density of $N = 10^{23} \text{ m}^{-3}$ to create each density profile.

is visible but weak, such that the low-order Taylor series approximation to the third-order drift-diffusion is applicable. More generally, the differences between the MC and second-order profiles can be much greater, especially at early times and in low pressure gases.

The approximate third-order solution agrees well with the MC simulation when compared to the second-order solution, particularly with respect to the location of the distribution peak, spread and asymmetry. There is noticeable discrepancy in the peak density at 20 ns, which is a consequence of the low-order Taylor series approximation to the third-order solution. The agreement further improves at 100 ns for both the second and third-order solutions with respect to the MC simulation, although a discrepancy in the positioning is still evident for the former. It is clear that the skewness coefficient has the potential to contribute substantially to the electron swarm behaviour and current trace shape.

To investigate the effect of the skewness on the remaining fitted transport coefficients (W_b , D_b , R_{net}), we have plotted the average relative error vs $\tilde{Q} = Q_b / \sqrt{T_e D_b^3}$ for each of the three targets in figure 7.

The parameter \tilde{Q} was identified by Simonovic *et al* [23] to represent the relative importance of the skewness effect, and a characteristic time scale of $t = T_e \equiv L/W_b$ was chosen. There is a clear positive correlation between the relative importance of skewness and the relative error, for each target and transport coefficient. The effect is most pronounced at low background densities (and pressures), and at small electrode gap distances. Note that even higher order transport coefficients will have some influence on the relative error shown here.

The relationship between background density (pressure), electrode gap distance and the skewness effect is made especially clear in figure 8, where the parameter \tilde{Q} is plotted vs E/N for the three targets.

A full characterisation of the physical effects of higher order transport will be undertaken in future work.

These results indicate that for certain small drift-time regimes, the PT experiment is not adequately described by the typical second-order drift-diffusion equation. In the regimes investigated we observe errors up to and exceeding 10% that can be attributed, for the most part, to the influence of skewness. When performing PT experiments, if the variation of either L or N is correlated to the fitted values of the transport coefficients, it is reasonable to assume that the contribution of skewness (or higher order transport) is significant. In this case, limiting measurements to larger N and L will likely lead to the most accurate results.

6. Conclusion

We use a MC solver to simulate waveforms obtained in a PT experiment and examine how experimental parameters such as gas pressure and electrode spacing influence the uncertainty in the obtained swarm parameters. As the swarm data is obtained by curve fitting analytical solutions of the drift-diffusion equation to the experimental waveforms, two sources of error are likely to dominate: (a) the source distributions and boundary conditions under which the analytical solution is derived do not match the experimental conditions and (b) higher order terms in the density gradient expansion are not taken into consideration.

From the discussion in section 5.1 it is clear that in order to obtain accurate values for R_{net} and W_b , measurements should preferably be carried out at high pressures and large electrode gap distances.

Especially in the case of R_{net} , where measurements at low pressures give a false apparent attachment at low fields. However, it is not always possible to carry out measurements at high pressures and large electrode gap distances as these conditions can lead to high space charge accumulation, which could again distort the results. This serves as motivation to further develop the fitting method.

When fitting experimentally measured current traces, the performed simulation study supports the use of measurements at lower pressures for obtaining D_b . This is experimentally also preferred due to a lower measurement uncertainty of D_b as the falling edge of the electron current waveforms is less distorted by measurement noise.

Comparing the results in section 5.1 for the representative case with those from section 5.2 for the idealised case, it is concluded that the pressure dependence of the $N \cdot D_b$ values commonly observed in experimental data originates, for the most part, from the mismatch between the experimental and theoretical boundary conditions. Particularly, the effects of back-diffusion to the cathode and an initial pulse width are not considered so far—this will be addressed within future work. At high fields, the fit values for R_{net} and W_b underestimate the true values, this appears to be largely due to third (and higher) order effects. Even in the idealised simulations with matching source distributions and boundary conditions to equation (6) the values are underestimated to a similar amount as that in the representative case. This effect is amplified in experiments as low pressures are typically used to enable measuring at very high field strengths without causing space-charge distortions or even breakdowns.

Significant errors of up to, and in excess of, 10% were demonstrated in the idealised case. This motivated the investigation of the influence of the third-order transport coefficient, which is neglected in the derivation of equation (6), and show that there is a strong correlation between the errors observed in the idealised case and the contribution of the third order coefficient. In light of the issues identified here, future work will focus on accounting for initial source and boundary conditions as well as skewness in the extraction of swarm transport coefficients.

Finally the fitting code is made available online under open access, and we hope this allows for precise understanding of the assumptions under which the experimental swarm data is derived and for a more consistent description of the obtained swarm data across the several groups that measure using the PT experiment. It is planned that future publications not only show the derived swarm parameters, but that also the measured current traces are made available as complementary material.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study will be openly available following an embargo at the following URL/DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656656> [49].

Acknowledgments

The High Voltage Lab at ETH Zürich gratefully acknowledges the financial support of ABB Schweiz AG, Hitachi Energy, GE Vernova, and Siemens AG as part of an industrial collaboration, and the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation project under Grant Agreement No. 101135484 (EU project MISSION). D. L. Muccignat and R. D. White gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Australian Research Council (ARC) through the Discovery Projects Scheme (DP220101480 and DP190100696). The authors would like to thank S Dujko, I Simonović, D. Bošnjaković and N A Garland for the valuable discussions.

Appendix A. Difficulties in curve fitting

Figure 9 shows some example simulated current traces, where a curve fitting with equation (6) is challenging. We make the following observations:

- (a) In the case of figure 9(a), the gas (SF_6) at the given conditions ($N = 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$, $E/N = 100 \text{ Td}$) is strongly attaching and the electron pulse does not manage to reach the anode boundary. This results in an exponentially decreasing current trace, which makes it difficult to distinguish between R_{net} and D_b . Thus, only the effective ionisation rate R_{net} can be practically determined in such a case.
- (b) In the example of figure 9(b), curve fitting with equation (6) cannot entirely capture the initial part of the waveform as the falling edge is noticeably skewed due to higher order effects such as Q_b . This feature is more noticeable at lower background densities (see also figures 4 and 10) as, e.g. Q_b scales with $1/N^2$.

Figure 9. Example simulated current traces that are challenging to evaluate for the three swarm parameters W_b , D_b and R_{net} using equation (6). The waveform in (a) is for SF₆ gas (*idealised PT*) at strongly attaching conditions, where subsequently only R_{net} can be determined. The trace in (b) is for Ar gas (*idealised PT*) at low density N , where Q_b is relatively large and the waveform, thus, noticeably skewed. This results in a more attaching R_{net} than is actually the case. Lastly, (c) is for CO₂ gas at low density N (*representative*), where the waveform is even more distorted due to the inclusion of the source distribution and a cathode boundary condition. In this case, electron back-diffusion to the cathode is visually evident from the initial peaking of the trace.

- (c) In figure 9(c), a low density current trace (in CO₂ gas) including the source distributions and both boundary conditions (i.e. the *representative* case) is shown. This results in an even stronger distortion of the current trace. In this particular case, the impact of the cathode boundary is also visually evident from the initial peak that results from electron back-diffusion. When evaluating with equation (7), the initial part needs to be cropped-off and the remaining distorted waveform is perceived as increasingly attaching.

These examples illustrate that waveform distortions arising from strong attachment, skewness, or boundary interactions can significantly degrade the reliability of the current curve fitting framework, underscoring the need to account for additional effects in the analysis of modern PT experiments.

Appendix B. Simulation of the Pulsed Townsend experiment: Argon and SF₆

Figures 10 and 11 show the respective representative and idealised results for Ar, as described in sections 5.1 and 5.2. Similarly, figures 12 and 13 show the respective representative and idealised results for SF₆.

For Ar, deviations between fitted and simulated parameters for R_{net} and W_b are more pronounced at low densities and low reduced electric fields, consistent with the observations for CO₂. In contrast, low densities lead to more accurate values of ND_b in CO₂ whereas in Ar this is reversed, figure 10.

In the case of SF₆, the strong electron attachment leads to a rapid decay in the current signal. As discussed in appendix A, this makes reliable extraction of both drift velocity and diffusion challenging. Similar to CO₂, in both gases the effect of neglecting the third-order terms is most evident in the longitudinal diffusion coefficient, where the fitted values significantly underestimate the actual values, figures 11 and 13. At low pressure, the influence of skewness becomes increasingly important, manifesting in distorted waveform shapes even under idealised conditions.

These results reinforce that curve fitting using second-order drift-diffusion models may yield inaccurate swarm parameters in certain regimes, and that the interpretation of PT waveforms must consider both the gas-specific physics and the limitations of the analytic model.

Figure 10. Swarm parameters in Ar gas from curve fitting with equation (6) to MC simulation waveforms within a setup that approximates the source distributions and boundary conditions of a realistic PT experiment. Experimental data from the UNAM [43, 44] and ETHZ database [45, 46] on LXCat is included for comparison. R_{net} values are measured at 3 kPa. There are significant deviations present between the swarm parameters obtained from curve fitting and the swarm parameters computed from MC simulations. The swarm parameters from curve fitting also show an apparent pressure dependency. Very high relative error percentages in the case of R_{net} are due to the true value of R_{net} being close to 0. Large uncertainties in D_b are due to poor fitting as described in appendix A.

Figure 11. Swarm parameters in Ar gas from curve fitting with equation (6) to MC simulation waveforms within an idealised setup that matches the source distributions and boundary conditions used when deriving equation (6). There are significant deviations in the swarm parameters in the case of: low gas densities (pressures) such as $N = 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-3}$, large reduced fields E/N , and small electrode gap distances L .

ORCID iDs

Hanut Vemulapalli 0000-0002-2332-1478

Mücahid Akbas 0009-0004-6979-0642

Dale Muccignat 0000-0002-6693-6851

Greg Boyle 0000-0002-8581-4307

Ron D White 0000-0001-5353-7440

Christian M Franck 0000-0002-2201-7327

References

- [1] Laroussi M 2009 Low-temperature plasmas for medicine? *IEEE Trans. Plasma Sci.* **37** 714–25
- [2] Oehrlein G S and Hamaguchi S 2018 Foundations of low-temperature plasma enhanced materials synthesis and etching *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **27** 023001
- [3] Ventzek P, Rauf S, Stout P, Zhang D, Dauksher W and Hall E 2002 Application and simulation of low temperature plasma processes in semiconductor manufacturing *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **192** 201–15
- [4] Li X, Zhao H and Murphy A B 2018 SF₆-alternative gases for application in gas-insulated switchgear *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **51** 153001
- [5] Stocco D, Metting van Rijn M and Franck C M 2024 Pulsed townsend electron and ion swarm parameter measurements of the trigger RPC standard mixture *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. A* **1064** 169441
- [6] Charles C 2009 Plasmas for spacecraft propulsion *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **42** 163001
- [7] Puač N, Gherardi M and Shiratani M 2018 Plasma agriculture: a rapidly emerging field *Plasma Process. Polymers* **15** 1700174
- [8] Adamovich I et al 2022 The 2022 plasma roadmap: low temperature plasma science and technology *J. Appl. Phys.* **55** 373001
- [9] Petrović Z L, Dujko S, Marić D, Malović G, Nikitović Ž, Šašić O, Jovanović J, Stojanović V and Radmilović-Radenović M 2009 Measurement and interpretation of swarm parameters and their application in plasma modelling *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **42** 194002
- [10] Huxley L and Crompton R 1974 Diffusion and drift of electrons in gases (available at: https://inis.iaea.org/search/search.aspx?orig_q=RN:6169870)
- [11] Haeffliger P and Franck C M 2018 Detailed precision and accuracy analysis of swarm parameters from a Pulsed Townsend experiment *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **89** 023114
- [12] Casey M J, Stokes P W, Cocks D G, Bošnjaković D, Simonović I, Brunger M J, Dujko S, Petrović Z L, Robson R E and White R D 2021 Foundations and interpretations of the pulsed-Townsend experiment *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **30** 035017
- [13] Bianchi A, Ferretti A, Gagliardi M and Vercellin E 2024 Electron collision cross sections in tetrafluoropropene HFO1234ze(E) for gas mixtures in resistive plate chambers *Eur. Phys. J. Plus* **139** 647
- [14] Šašić O, Dupljanin S, Dujko S and Petrović Z L 2025 Electron collision cross sections for 1,1,1,2-tetrafluoroethane (C₂H₂F₄) obtained by swarm analysis of transport coefficients in pure gas and its mixtures with argon *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **34** 045011
- [15] Stokes P W, Cocks D G, Brunger M J and White R D 2020 Determining cross sections from transport coefficients using deep neural networks *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **29** 055009
- [16] Jetly V and Chaudhury B 2021 Extracting electron scattering cross sections from swarm data using deep neural networks *Mach. Learn.: Sci. Technol.* **2** 035025
- [17] Muccignat D L, Boyle G G, Garland N A, Stokes P W and White R D 2024 An iterative deep learning procedure for determining electron scattering cross-sections from transport coefficients *Mach. Learn.: Sci. Technol.* **5** 015047
- [18] Flynn M, Agan J, Neuber A and Stephens J 2023 Generation and optimization of cross-sections for electron-C₄F₇N collisions *J. Appl. Phys.* **56** 485207
- [19] Kumar K, Skullerud H and Robson R E 1980 Kinetic theory of charged particle swarms in neutral gases *Aust. J. Phys.* **33** 343–448
- [20] Sakai Y, Tagashira H and Sakamoto S 1977 The development of electron avalanches in argon at high E/N values. I. monte carlo simulation *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **10** 1035
- [21] Tagashira H, Sakai Y and Sakamoto S 1977 The development of electron avalanches in argon at high E/N values. II. Boltzmann equation analysis *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **10** 1051
- [22] Robson R 1984 Generalized einstein relation and negative differential conductivity in gases *Aust. J. Phys.* **37** 35–44
- [23] Simonović I, Bošnjaković D, Petrović Z L, Stokes P, White R D and Dujko S 2020 Third-order transport coefficient tensor of charged-particle swarms in electric and magnetic fields *Phys. Rev. E* **101** 023203
- [24] Simonović I, Bošnjaković D, Petrović Z L, White R D and Dujko S 2020 Third-order transport coefficient tensor of electron swarms in noble gases *Eur. Phys. J. D* **74** 1–13
- [25] Simonović I, Bošnjaković D, Petrović Z L, White R and Dujko S 2022 Third-order transport coefficients for electrons in N₂ and CF₄: effects of non-conservative collisions, concurrence with diffusion coefficients and contribution to the spatial profile of the swarm *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **31** 015003
- [26] Kawaguchi S, Takahashi K and Satoh K 2023 Data-driven discovery of electron continuity equations in electron swarm map for determining electron transport coefficients in argon *J. Appl. Phys.* **56** 244003
- [27] Robson R 1985 Diffusion corrections in electron conductance transients *Phys. Rev. A* **31** 3492
- [28] Vemulapalli H and Franck C M 2023 Pulsed Townsend measurements with mixtures of C₄F₇N and C₅F₁₀O up to 1800 Td *J. Appl. Phys.* **56** 065202
- [29] Chachereau A, Hösl A and Franck C M 2018 Electrical insulation properties of the perfluoronitrile C₄F₇N *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **51** 495201
- [30] Virtanen P et al SciPy 1.0Contributors 2020 SciPy 1.0: fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in python *Nat. Methods* **17** 261–72
- [31] Brennan M 1991 Optimization of Monte Carlo codes using null collision techniques for experimental simulation at low E/N *IEEE Trans. Plasma Sci.* **19** 256–61
- [32] Muccignat D 2018 Monte Carlo simulation of non-equilibrium electron-liquid transport *PhD Dissertation* James Cook University
- [33] Skullerud H R 1968 The stochastic computer simulation of ion motion in a gas subjected to a constant electric field *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **1** 1567

- [34] Boyle G J, Tattersall W J, Cocks D G, McEachran R P and White R D 2017 A multi-term solution of the space–time Boltzmann equation for electrons in gases and liquids *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **26** 024007
- [35] Stokes P 2018 Anomalous charged-particle transport in organic and soft-condensed matter *PhD Dissertation* James Cook University
- [36] Boyle G J, Casey M J E, Cocks D G, White R D and Carman R J 2019 Thermalisation time of electron swarms in xenon for uniform electric fields *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **28** 035009
- [37] Boyle G J, Stokes P W, Robson R E and White R D 2023 Boltzmann’s equation at 150: traditional and modern solution techniques for charged particles in neutral gases *J. Chem. Phys.* **159** 024306
- [38] Biagi S F 2004 Biagi-v7.1 database
- [39] Pitchford L C *et al* 2017 LXCat: an Open-Access, web-based platform for data needed for modeling low temperature plasmas *Plasma Process. Polym.* **14** 1600098
- [40] Skullerud H 1974 Electron diffusion in gases *Aust. J. Phys.* **27** 195
- [41] McIntosh A I 1974 Computer simulation of an electron swarm at low E/p in Helium *Aust. J. Phys.* **27** 59–72
- [42] Penetrante B M and Bardsley J N 1990 Higher-Order Electron Transport in Gases *Nonequilibrium Effects in Ion and Electron Transport* ed J W Gallagher, D F Hudson, E E Kunhardt and R J Van Brunt (Springer) pp 49–66
- [43] UNAM database (available at: www.lxcat.net) (Retrieved on 13 June 2025)
- [44] Hernández-Ávila J L, Basurto E and de Urquijo J 2002 Electron transport and swarm parameters in CO₂ and its mixtures with SF₆ *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **35** 2264
- [45] ETHZ database (available at: www.lxcat.net) (Retrieved on 12 June 2025)
- [46] Hösl A, Chachereau A, Pachin J and Franck C M 2019 Identification of the discharge kinetics in the perfluoro-nitrile C₄F₇N with swarm and breakdown experiments *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **52** 235201
- [47] Christophorou L G and Olthoff J K 2000 Electron interactions with SF₆ *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data* **29** 267–330
- [48] Egüz E A, Pachin J and Franck C M 2022 Discussion on the mechanism leading to positive synergism in SF₆ mixtures with HFO1234ze(E) *J. Appl. Phys.* **55** 315203
- [49] Vemulapalli H, Akbas M, Muccignat D, Boyle G, White R and Franck C 2025 On the drift-diffusion analysis of the Pulsed Townsend experiment: a fitting algorithm and benchmark study *Zenodo* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656656>)